

On The Solutions Of Fermat's Diophantine Equation In 3-refined Neutrosophic Ring of Integers

Maretta Sarkis

Abu Dhabi University, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

Sarkismaretta1990@gmail.com

Abstract:

This work is dedicated to study the Fermat's Diophantine equation over the 3-refined neutrosophic ring of integers, where we provide an algorithm to find all triples that represent solutions of this non-linear Diophantine equation.

Keywords: 3-refined neutrosophic ring, Fermat's equation, non-linear Diophantine equation

Introduction

Neutrosophic number theory began with many efforts to study the Diophantine equations and many different types of neutrosophic integers in [2,3,5]. As a good example of non-linear Diophantine neutrosophic equation, we find the Fermat's Diophantine equation [1,4], where it was studied for neutrosophic and refined neutrosophic integers.

Fermat's Diophantine equation is defined as follows:

$$X^n + Y^n = Z^n ; \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Its solutions are called Fermat's general triples.

In this work we discuss this Diophantine equation in the case of 3-refined neutrosophic ring of integers.

Main Discussion

Definition.

Let R be a ring, a triple (X, Y, Z) is called general Fermat's triple if $X^n + Y^n = Z^n ; \forall n \in N$.

Definition.

Let R be a ring, the 3-refined neutrosophic ring is defined as follows:

$$R_3(I) = \{a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2 + a_3I_3\}, \text{ with } I_i^2 = I_i, I_i \cdot I_j = I_{\min(i,j)}.$$

If $R = Z$, then $R_3(I)$ is called the ring of 3-refined neutrosophic of integers.

Theorem.

Let $X = x_0 + x_1I_1 + x_2I_2 + x_3I_3 \in Z_3(I)$, then:

$$X^n = x_0^n + I_1[(x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3)^n - (x_0 + x_2 + x_3)^n] + I_2[(x_0 + x_2 + x_3)^n - (x_0 + x_3)^n] + I_3[(x_0 + x_3)^n - x_0^n] \text{ for all } n \in N.$$

Remark.

The equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$ where $X = x_0 + x_1I_1 + x_2I_2 + x_3I_3, Y = y_0 + y_1I_1 + y_2I_2 + y_3I_3, Z = z_0 + z_1I_1 + z_2I_2 + z_3I_3$ equivalent:

$$\begin{cases} x_0^n + y_0^n = z_0^n \\ (x_0 + x_3)^n + (y_0 + y_3)^n = (z_0 + z_3)^n \\ (x_0 + x_2 + x_3)^n + (y_0 + y_2 + y_3)^n = (z_0 + z_2 + z_3)^n \\ (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3)^n + (y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3)^n = (z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3)^n \end{cases}$$

This is equivalent to:

$(x_0, y_0, z_0), (x_0 + x_3, y_0 + y_3, z_0 + z_3), (x_0 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_2 + z_3), (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3)$ are Fermat's triples in Z .

Fermat's triples in Z are $(1,0,1), (0,1,1), (0,0,0)$.

To find Fermat's triples in $Z_3(I)$, we discuss the following:

Cases.

Case1:

If $(x_0, y_0, z_0) = (x_0 + x_3, y_0 + y_3, z_0 + z_3) = (x_0 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_2 + z_3) = (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3) = (0,0,0)$, we get $(X, Y, Z) = (0,0,0)$.

Case2:

If $(x_0, y_0, z_0) = (1,0,1), (x_0 + x_3, y_0 + y_3, z_0 + z_3) = (x_0 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_2 + z_3) = (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3) = (0,0,0)$, we get $(X, Y, Z) = (1 - I_3, 0, 1 - I_3)$.

Case3:

$(X, Y, Z) = (0, 1 - I_3, 1 - I_3)$.

Case4:

If $(x_0, y_0, z_0) = (x_0 + x_3, y_0 + y_3, z_0 + z_3) = (1, 0, 1)$, $(x_0 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_2 + z_3) = (x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3) = (0, 0, 0)$, we get $(X, Y, Z) = (1 - I_2, 0, 1 - I_2)$.

Case5:

$(X, Y, Z) = (0, 1 - I_2, 1 - I_2)$.

Case6:

$(X, Y, Z) = (1, 0, 1)$.

Case7:

$(X, Y, Z) = (0, 1, 1)$.

Case8:

If $(x_0, y_0, z_0) = (x_0 + x_3, y_0 + y_3, z_0 + z_3) = (x_0 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_2 + z_3) = (1, 0, 0)$, $(x_0 + x_1 + x_2 + x_3, y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3, z_0 + z_1 + z_2 + z_3) = (0, 0, 0)$, we get $(X, Y, Z) = (1 - I_1, 0, 1 - I_1)$.

Case9:

$(X, Y, Z) = (0, 1 - I_1, 1 - I_1)$.

Case10:

$(X, Y, Z) = (I_1, 0, I_1)$.

Case11:

$(X, Y, Z) = (0, I_1, I_1)$.

Case12:

$(X, Y, Z) = (I_2, 0, I_2)$.

Case13:

$(X, Y, Z) = (0, I_2, I_2)$.

Case14:

$(X, Y, Z) = (I_3, 0, I_3)$.

Case15:

$(X, Y, Z) = (0, I_3, I_3)$.

By continuing this argument, we get all desired solutions.

References

- [1] Ali, R., "A Short Note On The Solution of n-Refined Neutrosophic Linear Diophantine Equations", International Journal Of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 15, 2021.
- [2] Ibrahim, M., and Abobala, M., "An Introduction To Refined Neutrosophic Number Theory", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 45, 2021.
- [3] Ceven, Y., and Tekin, S., "Some Properties of Neutrosophic Integers", Kırklareli University Journal of Engineering and Science, Vol. 6, 2020.

[4] Ahmad, K., Bal, M., and Aswad, M., " A Short Note On The Solutions Of Fermat's Diophantine Equation In Some Neutrosophic Rings", Journal Of Neutrosophic and Fuzzy Systems, 2022.

[5] Abobala, M., Partial Foundation of Neutrosophic Number Theory, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 39 , 2021.